

Effect of Market Orientation on Organizational Performance: The Mediating Role of Entrepreneurial and Innovation Capability Multiple Regression Model: In Oromia Regional State West Guji Zone Coffee Trading and Factory Enterprise's PLC

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Abstract – The study that provides, a conceptual linear Regression Model that introduction to analyses a meditating variables, conditional effect process macro data analysis in behavioral science Business research, and to discuss the concepts of linear regression data analysis to be a Direct influence, indirect influence, Total Influence, conditional Influence, and the indexed of mediation result to be providing based on our perspective on certain analysis, and the overall the mediating variable data analysis to be interpreting the multiple linear regression analyses in a model that includes a Mediating influence of EO, Innovational Orientation that affect MO and Organizational Performance to investigate by Macro data process analysis, that influenced multiple linear regression influence depends on Entrepreneurial Orientation, and Innovation mediating data, and to investigate with Process Macro v.4 with SPSS model V.25 that uses data from the Market Orientation to analyse it's effect with Organizational Performance with mediating role of Entrepreneurial Orientation and Innovation capability by using 380 sample respondents in Oromia Regional state West Guji Zone Coffee Trading and Factories PLC.

Keywords: Market Orientation, Organizational Performance, Enterprnioure Orientation Innovation, Coffee trading and Factory PLC.

1. INTRODUCTION

In Business Market orientation that is the most essential, effective business, efficient business with independent business organizational culture to expand business activity, and to creating the essential behavior of business, and to produce superior high value for buyers, so that the continuous, and superior Organizational performance can be achieved, (Tseng et al., 2019), and MO of a corporate research business to need business culture that can lead a company, and to improve a business Organizational performance, Shan et al. (2016), and the company that makes MO practice of an organizational performance that based on External and Internal needs of the business market conditions, that has to be formulating strategies for the organization success, and determining the success of the business organizational achievement, competition orientation, Customer Orientation and inter-functional Orientation to be investigated, (Usvita, M. 2020), and EO practice attitudes are closely related to policies, and real work and basic business practices to develop Entrepreneurial Orientation actions of business Organization (Martens et al., 2017), and state that entrepreneur orientation can describe the company's process of entering new markets culture through aggressiveness, Anatomy, innovativeness, risk-taking, proactive attitude (Shaher & Ali, 2020).

Gada Gizachew Wakjira (2022), the Innovational Marketing capability is an idea, and a method to search a business, and is limited to business products, and services that are perceived as something new, (Siagian & Ikatrinasari, 2019), and Innovation Marketing capability to be something that is completely new business ideology on the basis of the thoughts, or views of people saying that the ideas, or actions are new, and innovation business capability of a new idea that is applied to initiate, and to improve a product, process or service (Rahmat et al., 2021).

Gada Gizachew Wakjira (2021), Coffee trading and Factory PLC. it is a crucial role to improving the International business economy, (Susana & Andarwati, 2021), and PLC to be contributed up to 40% of (GDP), and have been creating new product needs opportunity, and PLC had the resilience in driving the economy even in extreme business conditions, (Sinuraya, 2020), and Organizational performance is a company's ability to adapt to changed Organizational environment, and develop a good organizational business strategy that complements management's ability to create harmony launch new product between social of surrounding external PLC, and internal company Coffee PLC, (Zainudin & Sugiono, 2019).

The problem that has to be trapped EO, Innovation Marketing capability, by reactive the MO is higher contribution in developing countries, were as Ethiopian Coffee Trading and Factory PLC manufacturing area that belong, for reasons that organization in Ethiopia has a lower understanding of Market Orientation practices, lack of Competitor Orientation lack of Customer Orientation, Lack of Inter- functional Coordination access to raw materials, lack of market access, stiff competition from foreign competitors, and lack of technological capacity of marketing capability even to predict in the future marketing business trends, to let alone to devise proactive marketing strategies. Thus, in addition to the gap in managerial practices, there is also a, Historical literature gap, theoretical gap, Evidence gap, Empirical gap and Methodological gap, data analyses gap to be view in multiple linear regression model, in data research investigation market orientation on Organizational performance the mediation role of Enterprnioure Orientation and Innovation capability in Coffee trading and Factory PLC in Ethiopia has limited, (Aschalew Degoma Beshir & Elias Shetemam, 2018).

Therefore, this study will be aimed at determining the effect of Market orientation and Organizational Performance, and to investigate the mediating influence of Entrepreneurial Orientation and Innovation of Oromia Regional State West Guji Zone Coffee Trading and Factory PLC Enterprise's.

2. OBJECTIVE INVESTIGATION

1. To assess the direct relationship between Market Orientation practice and Business Performance of Coffee trading and Factory PLC.
2. To analysis the direct relationship between Entrepreneurial Orientation and Business Performance Coffee trading and Factory PLC.
3. To assess the direct relationship between innovation and Business Performance Coffee trading and Factory PLC.
4. To examine the direct relationship of Market Orientation with Enterprnioure Orientation of trading and Factory PLC.
5. To describe the direct relationship of Market Orientation with Innovation of Coffee trading and Factory PLC.

6. To determine the Entrepreneurial Orientation mediation role through Market Orientation and business Performance of Coffee trading and Factory PLC.

7. To evaluate the Innovation capability Mediation role through Market Orientation and business Performance of Coffee trading & Factory PLC.

3. CONCEPTUAL MODEL DESIGN

Fig -1: Conceptual Model Design

Source: Value of AMOS output (2023)

4. INVESTIGATION APPROACH AND DESIGN

Quantitative research approach the quantitative approach will be served research in many ways and the justifications support why quantitative approach will be selected forth is research most of the empirical investigations in coffee trading and factory PLC, has to be conducted by adopting quantitative approach in their designs to determine an expected relationships which might emerge from interaction between a set of given research variables, and this approach that has to be designed Explanatory research designed that has to be developed the mediation variable of Enterprinioure Orientation, Market Innovation that affect Market Orientation on Organizational Performance of coffee trading and factory PLC enterprises of Ethiopia that Mediation data has designed Multiple linear Regression Coefficient that has to be analysed, Conditional data effect, total Effect, Direct effect, indirect Effect, and Blanco-Donoso, L. (2019), Conditional Effect process model is a mediation model, and there are indirect and direct effects. We have shown that the indirect effect, with the evidence of mediation of total effect of similarity, and feelings through identification in the first-person, but not the third-person narrative voice condition to designed, Hayes, A. F. (2022), with Primary and Secondary Cooperative Union, Coffee supplier, Coffee Collector, Employee of PLC to collect from Oromia Regional state West Guji Zone Coffee trading and Factory seven PLC, Namely Kercha Inshe Coffee trading PLC, Sakicha Coffee trading PLC, Guji Highland Coffee Plantation Factory PLC, Tamirat Zarihun Coffee factory PLC, Ethiopia Natural Gerba Guji Coffee factory PLC, and Kadir Abba Hawa Coffee trading and factory PLC, and data collected from 380 Respondents, and Research technique to be designed with Simple random techniques and Stratified sampling technique has to be designed in Oromia Regional state West Guji zone Coffee trading and Factory Knoster, K. C., & Goodboy, A. K. (2020).

5. MULTIPLE LINEAR REGRESSION DATA ANALYSES

Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adj. R Square	Std. Err.
	.858a	.735	.733	.44457

a. Predictors: Innovation Capability, Market Orientation, Enterprnioure Orientation

Sebastian Taylor (2023), the estimated Multiple linear regression coefficients and their R= .0858 R²= 0735, Adj. R²= .733, Std. Err. =.44457, and the information is displayed in data set, Tamoskova, E. (2018) due to this reseon Market orientation with Organizational performance, Innovation with Organizational performance and Enterprnioure Orientation with Organizational performance is significantly the alternative hypotheses value output result of R= high Correlation value, R square value output .735 to solve the problem the remaining problem that solve by other variables and the variance value Adjusted R Square result is .733 by 2 variance this means higher value of Model summary that support in this study, in Oromia Regional state West Guji Zone Coffee trading and Factory PLC, R.H, P. J. (2016).

ANOVA

Model	Sum Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	206.571	3	68.857	348.392	.000b
Residual	74.313	376	.198		
Total	280.884	379			

a. Dependent Variable: OP

b. Predictors of ICMO and EO

N., Nwankwo, S., & Trang, T.P. (2016) The Analyses of Variance output result Model over all Regression Model of, MO, and EO, innovation that affect OP of Coffee trading and Factory PLC result output shows the total Sum of Squares value 280.884, df= 3+376= 379, Mean Square value MSR= 68.857 and MSE value .198 that means F Calculation output result MSR/MSE= 348.392 with value result of .000, this means the value $p < .001$, due to this reseon Market orientation with Organizational performance, Innovation with Organizational performance and Enterprnioure Orientation with Organizational performance is significantly the alternative hypotheses value output result has positively significant and supported in Oromia Regional state West Guji Zone Coffee trading and Factory PLC.

Coefficient

Model	Unstained. Coefficients		Standardize Coefficients	t-Value	P-Value
	B	Std. Err.	Beta		
(Variables)	9.699	.363		26.749	.000
Market Orientation	.229	.024	.286	9.604	.000
Enterprnioure Orientation	.258	.024	.342	10.693	.000
Innovation	.328	.022	.460	14.986	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Performance

Sebastian Taylor (2023), Regression analysed data value of Market Orientation with Organizational performance, Enterprnioure Orientation with Organizational Performance, and Innovation with Organizational performance of Standardized Coefficients ($Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + e$), this means Y_1 intercept value = $9.969 (\beta_0) + 286 \beta_1 (\beta_{MO}) + .342 \beta_2 (\beta_{EO}) + .460 \beta_3 (\beta_{INN}) + .363$, this means with constant value result $9.699 + .286 + .342 + .460 + .022$ value, and Constant t = Value result 26.749, based on this out put the significant Value result H_1, H_2 and H_3 P. value output .000 this means the value $p < 0.001$, due to this reason Independent Variable with Dependent Variable, Innovation Capability with Firm performance and Enterprnioure Orientation with Organizational performance is significantly the alternative hypotheses value of linear predictor, output result has positively significantly supported in Oromia Regional state West Guji Zone Coffee trading and Factory PLC.

H1: Market Orientation practice has a direct relationship positive with Business Performance of Coffee trading and Factory of PLC.

H2: Entrepreneurial Orientation has a direct positive relationship with Business Performance Coffee trading and Factory of PLC.

H3: innovation Capability has a direct positive relationship with Business Performance Coffee trading and Factory of PLC.

Coefficient

Model	Unstained. Coefficients		Standardize Coefficients	t-Value	P-Value
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
	7.337	.693		10.585	.000
Market Orientation	.454	.049	.429	9.221	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Enterprnioure Orientation

The Effect of Market Orientation that influenced Enterprnioure Orientation the unstandardized Coefficient Constant value result is 7.337 the highest Beta value 0.454, the Standardized Coefficients Beta .429, t= value constant value 10.585and 9.221 and the significant Value result is .000 this means the value $p < .001$, due to this reseon Market Innovation that affect Enterprnioure Orientation in Coffee trading and Factory PLC is supported.

Ha4: Market Orientation has a direct relationship with Enterprnioure Orientation of trading and Factory of PLC.

Coefficient

Model	Unstained. Coefficients		Standardize Coefficients	t-Value	P-Value
	B	Std. Err.	Beta		
Market Orientation	8.900	.764		11.654	.000
	.382	.054	.341	7.043	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Innovation Capability

The Effect of Market Orientation that influenced Enterprnioure Orientation the unstandardized Coefficient Constant value result is 8.900 the highest Beta value 0.382, with the standard error value 0.764, the Standardized Coefficients Beta 0.341, t= value constant value 11.654and 7.043and the significant Value result is .000 this means the value $p\text{-value} < .001$, due to this reseon Market Innovation that affect Enterprnioure Orientation in Coffee trading and Factory PLC is supported.

H5: Market Orientation has significant positive relationship with Innovation capability of Coffee trading and Factory PLC.

Fig -2: Value of output (2023)

6. MEDIATION VARIABLE OF DATA ANALYSES

Model: 4

Y: ORGPE

X: MAROR

M1: EOCAP

M2: INNOCAP

Sample Size: **380**

Outcome Variables

EOCAP

Model Summary

R	R2	MSE	f	df1	df2	p
.6285	.4836	1.0629	85.0218	1.0000	378.0000	.0000

Model

	Coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	7.3374	.6932	10.5849	.0000	5.9744	8.7004
EOCAP	.4544	.0493	9.2207	.0000	.3575	.5513

Covariance matrix of multiple linear regressions Model of parameter estimates

Variable	MAROR	
Variable	.4805	-.0341
MAROR	-.0341	.0024

Outcome Variables

INNOCAP

Model Summary

R	R2	MSE	f	df1	df2	p
.5406	.3160	1.2902	49.5999	1.0000	378.0000	.0000

Model

	Coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Variable	8.9002	.7637	11.6538	.0000	7.3985	10.4019
INNOCAP	.3823	.0543	7.0427	.0000	.2756	.4891

Covariance matrix of multiple linear regressions Model of parameter estimates

Variable	MAROR
Variable	

Variable	.5833	-.0413
MAROR	-.0413	.0029

ORGPE

Model Summary

R	R2	MSE	f	df1	df2	p- Value
.8576	.7354	.1976	348.3916	3.0000	376.0000	.0000

The estimated multiple linear regression coefficients of mediating data variables, and their standard errors, the p-values, the R2, and the information is displayed in data set. Each of the three conditional process models representing Market Orientation, Enterprnioure Oriented and Innovation Capability, and Firm performance with a significant with R= Market Orientation 0.5893, Enterprnioure orientation 0.628, Innovation.5406, and Organizational performance 0.8576 R2= Market Orientation 0.3473, Enterprnioure orientation 0.4836, Innovation 0.3160, and Organizational performance ranging from.

Model

	Coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	9.6987	.3626	26.7487	.0000	8.9857	10.4116
MAROR	.2292	.0239	9.6041	.0000	.1823	.2761
EOCAP	.2582	.0241	10.6931	.0000	.2107	.3056
INNOCAP	.3284	.0219	14.9856	.0000	.2853	.3715

Regression analysed data value for MO (.2292, p- value <001), with EO (.2582, p- value < 001) to be a significant, Innovation Capability value (0.3284, p- value < 001), and OP (0.4720, p<0.001) consequent, and Mediation Enterprnioure is a significant Relationship with Market Orientation and Organizational Performance Enterprnioure orientation (.4544), and Moreover the conditional effects of X and Y with M to be shows with their product in the model has negative coefficient (negative effect) of -0.065 and statistically not significant (p = 0.000**).

To test of X by M interaction:

	F	df1	df2	p. value
Mediation1*X	4.1173	1.0000	375	.0000
Mediation2*X	31.7983	1.0000	375	.0000

***** Total Effect Model *****

OUTCOME VARIABLE:

MAROR

Model summery.

(R)	R-square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p. value
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.5893 .3473 .4850 201.0961 1.0000 378.0000 .0000

Model

	Coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	14.5158	.4683	30.9990	.0000	13.5951	15.4365
MAROR	.4720	.0333	14.1808	.0000	.4066	.5375

***** Total Effects, Direct Effects, and Indirect Effects of X on Y *****

Total influence of X with Y

Effects	SE	t. Value	p	LLCI	ULCI
.4720	.0333	14.1808	.0000	.4066	.5375

Total Effect predict Variables of MO on OP with mediation role of EO the total effect result 0.4720, SE value result 0.0333, t= value 14.1808, LLCI= 0.4066 and ULCI= 0.5375 The index of mediation effects is -0.041 and the 95% bias corrected bootstrap confidence interval M1*X Enterprnioure Orientation that mediated between MO and OP F= 4.1173 df1= 1.0000 df2= 375.0000 p. Value= 0.0432, than the statistical inference with significance value p>0.001, for this reseon the mediation output value has to be supported to contribute business organization of West Guji Zone coffee trading and Factory PLC.

H6: Entrepreneurial Orientation has a mediated Negative relationship b/n Market Orientation and Organizational Performance of Coffee trading and Factory PLC with the p. Value= 0.432

Haroon R. Abbu, Pradeep Gopalakrishna (2019), Total influence of MO on OP with mediation role with Innovation Capability of the total effect result 0.4720, SE value result 0.0333, t= value 14.1808, LLCI= 0.4066 and ULCI= 0.5375, and the indexed of mediation influence is .041 with 95% confidence interval level M2*X Innovation that mediated between Market Orientation and Organizational Performance F= 31.7983 df1= 1.0000 df2= 375.0000 p. Value= .000 the statistical inference with significance value p<0.001.

H7: Innovation has a mediated positive relationship b/n Market Orientation and Organizational Performance of Coffee trading& Factory PLC.

Direct effect of X on Y

Effects	SE	T	p- Value	LLCI	ULCI
.2292	.0239	9.6041	.0000	.1823	.2761

The direct influence result of direct effect = 0 .2292 SE value = 0 .0239, t value = 9.6041 P. Value result= .0000 Lower limit Confidence Interval LLCI= .1823, and Upper limit Confidence Interval ULCI Value result .2761 based on this reseon the direct effect of independent variable of Market Orientation with Organizational Performance, Enterprnioure orientation with Organizational Performance, Innovation with Organizational Performance, Market Orientation with Enterprnioure, and Market orientation with Innovation P. Value result = .0000, with significance value p>0.001 based on this assumption the direct effect result independent variable Market orientation, mediation variable of Enterprnioure orientation, and Market Innovation and Dependent Variable Organizational performance of Coffee Trading and Factory PLC output has to be highly supported.

Indirect influence of X on Y:

	Effect	SE	LLCI	ULCI
TOTAL	.2429	.0277	.1906	.2982
EOCAP	.1173	.0187	.0835	.1559
INNOCAP	.1256	.0188	.0899	.1629
(CI)	-.0083	.0253	-.0601	.0411

Batailler, C., & Judd, C. M. (2018), that has recommends using the Indexed of Enterprnioure orientation of a total effect test for evidence of data influence of EO → MO→BP indirect effect value result 0.1173 Boot SE results 0.0187, LLCI result .0835, ULCI .1559 value this indexed analyses influenced with significance value $p < .001$ is supported to expand the Organizational center of PLC.

Jabbour, C. J. C. (2019), recommends using the index of Mediating variables of Innovation Capability of the most total effect test for evidence of mediation effect of INNO → MO→BP indirect effect value result .1256 Boot SE results .0188, LLCI result .0899, Upper limit Confidence Interval Boot ULCI 0.1629 value this index is then tested for statistical significance using bias-corrected bootstrapping for statistical inference with significance value $p < 0.001$, Pirlott, A. G., & MacKinnon, D. P. (2016) the specific indirect effect Contrast CI= Effect value -.0083 Boot SE .0253, LLCI -.0601, and ULCI .0411, with in the Confidence levels of all intervals in output, 95%, and Number of variables bootstrap samples for unit level of variable bootstrap confidence intervals value 5000 has to be significantly supported for the contribution of Market orientation. Mediation Enterprnioure orientation and innovation to support the Organizational performance to contribute Oromia Regional state West Guji zone Coffee trading and Factory PLC Andrew F. Hayes(2022).

7. CONCLUSION

Regression analysed data value of Market Orientation with Organizational performance, Enterprnioure Orientation with Organizational Performance, and Innovation with Organizational performance of Standardized Coefficients ($Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + e$), this means Y_1 intercept value = $9.969 (\beta_0) + 286 \beta_1 (\beta_{MO}) + .342 \beta_2 (\beta_{EO}) + .460 \beta_3 (\beta_{INN}) + .363$, this means with constant value result $9.699 + .286 + .342 + .460 + .022$ value, and Constant $t =$ Value result 26.749, based on this out put the significant Value result H_1, H_2 and H_3 P. value output .000 this means the value $p < 0.001$, due to this reseon independent Variable with Firm performance, Innovation Capability with Organizational performance and Enterprnioure Orientation with Organizational performance is significantly correlated , and the alternative hypotheses value of Multiple linear regression predictor, output result has positively significant and supported in Oromia Regional state West Guji Zone Coffee trading and Factory PLC.

The direct effect Value result of direct effect = 0 .2292 SE value = 0 .0239, t value = 9.6041 P. Value result = .0000 LLCI = .1823, and ULCI Value result .2761 based on this reseon the direct effect of independent variable of Market Orientation with Organizational Performance, Enterprnioure orientation with Organizational Performance, Innovation with Organizational Performance, Market Orientation with Enterprnioure, and Market orientation with Innovation P-Value result = .0000, with significance value $p > 0.001$ based on this assumption the direct effect result Market orientation, mediation variable of EO, and IC and with the Constant Variable with Organizational performance of Coffee Trading and Factory PLC output has to be highly supported.

Index of Mediation Enterprnioure orientation has to be a total influence test for evidence of mediation value of EO → MO→BP indirect effect value result .1173 Boot SE results .0187, Boot LLCI result .0835, Boot ULCI .1559 the value has tested to statistical significance using bias–corrected bootstrapping for statistical inference with significance p–Value<0.001 has supported to expand the Organizational center of PLC.

8. FURTHER RESEARCH DIRECTION

Depending to investigate to produce not only coffee trading and factory PLC in additional new product generate, like Maize, Haricot bean, Dairy, Oilseeds and pulse or the supply side, and to assess factor influencing Environmental Factor that affect Coffee marketing like Attitude, Amount of Rain fall, Availability of light, Temperature, and Weather Condition are assessed.

Therefore, it would be better for future study on Market Orientation and to develop Member Satisfaction, and effect of other facilities, Warehouse, Information, Traditional Production System, Price discovery from Harvest to member satisfaction by other influential variables which could affect Coffee Quality management practice for how to lead and aggravate market Expanding of Coffee and other commodity trading and factory of PLC enterprise's, are potential areas for further study.

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